

Deepening the consequences of multidisciplinary research: the moderating role of social capital

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Abstract

This paper discusses the relationship between multidisciplinary research and performance in the academic context. The paper explains how scholars' scientific performance is affected by the multidisciplinary nature of the network of colleagues with whom they conduct their research. Furthermore, this paper explores the potential moderating role of academics' social capital, assuming that relational dynamics can mitigate the potential problems associated with disciplinary diversity. To build the proposed model, the paper draws on previous literature on diversity and social capital. The resulting hypotheses are tested through a quantitative study developed on the basis of a sample of scholars in the field of management. Information about multidisciplinary research and performance was extracted from the Scopus database, while social capital variables were measured through social network analysis techniques. Econometric estimations were used to test the proposed relationships. The findings suggest that the effect of multidisciplinary research and researchers' performance can be depicted as an inverted U-shaped relationship, so an optimal intermediate level of diversity can be found. Estimations also show that relational, cognitive and structural social capital moderates this curvilinear relationship, making it possible to achieve higher research performance at higher levels of multidisciplinary research.

Keywords: Social Capital, Research, Diversity, Multidisciplinary

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in both domestic and international scientific collaboration (Coccia and Bozeman 2016), an increase that implies more complex relationships among individuals, groups, institutions and regions (Katz and Martin 1997). For this reason, scientific collaboration has become an important topic of research, attracting the interest of a wide range of disciplines, including research management studies (Liu and Xia 2015). The literature has provided different definitions of scientific collaboration and offered diverse reasons for engaging in it. For instance, Sonnenwald (2007:645) defined scientific collaboration as ‘interaction taking place within a social context among two or more scientists that facilitates the sharing of meaning and completion of tasks with respect to a mutually shared, superordinate goal’. Thus defined, scientific collaboration is linked to significant improvements in productivity, visibility and experience as well as access to special equipment, facilities and skills (Beaver and Rosen 1978; Andrade et al. 2009).

Although some authors have documented an increase in specialization and collaboration between scientists in some areas (e.g. Leahey and Reikowsky 2008), many of the research questions addressed by collaborative networks require a multidisciplinary approach. The use of multidisciplinary research groups is a feature of postmodern research that can also improve scientific advances, given the potential value of interactions among different research domains and disciplines (Van der Vegt and Bunderson 2005). Diversity is a characteristic of groups that manifests heterogeneity in some attribute of group members; multidisciplinary research groups are characterized by the diversity of disciplines of their members. Researchers from different academic backgrounds contribute to group projects with different explicit and tacit knowledge while creating synergy (Leonard and Sensiper 1998). Groups composed of members from diverse backgrounds generate more creative solutions and innovative outcomes, as empirical studies have shown (Cummings and Kiesler 2005; Guimera et al. 2005; Joshi and Roh 2009). However, to perform effectively, multidisciplinary groups must meet specific conditions related to identification, cohesion, communication and collaboration among team members (Perry-Smith and Vincent 2008).

To explain these complex effects of multidisciplinary on the performance of researchers, this paper reviews previous literature on group diversity to propose a model of the conditions under which research networks composed of academics from different disciplines perform most effectively. For the purpose of this study, and given the nature of academic research, we provide an informal definition of groups, focusing on the networks built by a focal researcher and their collaborators in Scopus-ranked publications, regardless of their disciplinary profile and institutional affiliations.

A large body of literature has recently expanded on the effects of the composition of work groups in terms of the relational-related and job-related attributes of their members, with no conclusive findings (Joshi and Roh 2009; Stahl et al. 2010). It is argued that diverse groups may benefit from broader perspectives and opinions, favouring problem-solving and decision-making processes (Cox and Blake 1991; Simons et al. 1999; Horwitz and Horwitz 2007; Martín-Alcázar et al. 2011). A wider range of knowledge, skills and abilities positively influences group performance (Williams and O'Really 1998; Hoever et al. 2012; Wang et al. 2016). However, communication and co-ordination problems increase, and more conflict may

also arise in heterogeneous groups (Tsui et al. 1992; Cummings and Kiesler 2005). Because of these opposing forces, heterogeneity is often described as a ‘two-edged sword’ (Weber and Donahue 2001).

The social capital literature suggests that social network structures affect the knowledge resources available to group members and thus the performance of the whole group (Nahapiet and Ghoshal 1998; Reagans and Zuckerman 2001; Wong 2008; Chung and Jackson 2012). Studies exploring the effects of diversity have emphasized the role of social networks, arguing that they could affect the way in which knowledge diversity influences the performance of new product development teams (Ancona and Caldwell 1992; Tsai et al. 2014), R&D industrial teams (Reagans and Zuckerman 2001; Curseu et al. 2012) or scientific academic groups (Liao 2011; Bercovitz and Friedman 2011). At the individual level, diversity knowledge network research has explained how exposure to structured social networks positively influences individual creativity or knowledge production and diffusion (Phelps et al. 2012). Moreover, in the literature about collaborative academic research, we find papers emphasizing the role of social networks, focusing on the relational, cognitive and structural dimensions of social capital (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013; Gonzalez-Brambila 2014).

As the empirical evidence indicates, the team diversity–performance relationship may be moderated by team-level contextual factors related to task complexity and interdependence (Horwitz and Horwith 2007; Joshi and Roh 2009; Bell et al. 2011). From this perspective, research on groups’ social capital may be an appropriate framework for analysing the conditions under which the disciplinary diversity of scientific research groups affects the productivity of researchers. This paper starts from the premise that previous literature on social capital can explain how the multidisciplinary of an academic network affects individual performance. As explained below, we assume that researchers’ social capital moderates this relationship by making it possible to take advantage of the positive effects of multidisciplinary and to mitigate its potential problems (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The moderating role of social capital

Source: Own elaboration

In this sense, the paper contributes in several ways. First, it combines three streams of literature such as team diversity, researcher performance and social capital. Second, it provides new evidence about the curvilinear relationship between disciplinary diversity and performance of researchers. It explains internal processes within multidisciplinary research units and how they affect the scientific performance of researchers. Third, it explores the potential moderating role

of the social capital of research groups and how relational dynamics can mitigate the potential problems associated with disciplinary diversity.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the theoretical arguments and the empirical evidence found in the review of the two streams of the literature from which the model is built: diversity and social capital. Section 3 describes the methodology applied to test the proposed model and the data gathering process. The results are discussed in section 4, and section 5 synthesizes the main conclusions, limitations of the study and future lines of research.

2. Literature review

2.1. Disciplinary diversity in research

The concept of diversity has been used with different meanings by researchers in the organizational and strategic management fields. Van Knippenberg and Schippers (2007) define diversity as ‘a characteristic of social grouping that reflects the degree to which objective or subjective differences exist between group members’. The idea of heterogeneity in a set of demographic factors between work group members underlies definitions of diversity. The attributes selected in each case to build this construct are different (Jackson et al. 2003). As van Dijk et al. (2012) note, diversity may refer to differences in demographic attributes (e.g., age, gender and ethnicity), job-related attributes (e.g., functional background, education and tenure), psychological characteristics (e.g., personality, attitudes and values) and other attributes that differ between members of a group.

Researchers exploring the influence of these attributes have found positive, negative and even non-significant effects of team diversity attributes on team processes (Tyran and Gibson 2008; Henttonen et al. 2010; Seong and Honh 2013), so a closer look at the specific consequences reviewed in each case is necessary.

The relationship between team diversity and performance has been analysed using diverse theoretical approaches. Information/decision-making theories consider that heterogeneous groups should perform better owing to their access to a greater variety of information, knowledge, abilities and skills (Williams and O’Reilly 1998). According to social categorization and social identity theories (Tajfel and Turner 1986) and the similarity–attraction paradigm (Byrne 1971), homogeneous groups would gain advantages over more diverse ones, for which the appearance of subgroups might be detrimental to group processes and performance (Hass 2010; Van Dijk et al. 2012). Individuals categorize themselves and others into subgroups and identify with groups perceived as similar to themselves in order to reduce potential conflicts or psychological consequences from cognitive differences (Lungeanu and Contractor 2015). The social identity of individuals motivates citizenship behaviours that favour co-operation with other in-group members (Janssen and Huang 2008). Demographic dissimilarity from out-groups helps team members to their enhance social identity and to see out-group members as less trustworthy, honest and co-operative than in-group members (Guillaume et al. 2012). Personal and social identities involve individual and collective conceptualizations of the self, respectively, and are related to both team performance and individual performance (Randel and Jaussi 2003). In contrast, the interpersonal congruence approach indicates that by expressing the individual characteristics that make them unique,

diverse groups with high interpersonal congruence among members could work together effectively, thus favouring the group's processes and performance (Polzer et al. 2002). Similarly, the integration and learning diversity perspective has implications for how groups benefit from their diversity (Ely and Thomas 2001).

Summarizing previous arguments, we can observe that relations-oriented diversity attributes (e.g., gender, race/ethnicity and age) are related to social categorization processes that may affect team processes and team performance negatively (Williams and O'Really 1998). Task-oriented diversity attributes (e.g., education, function and tenure) are associated with elaboration-based processes of the groups, which may explain the positive effects of team diversity on team performance (Joshi and Roh 2009; Van Knippenberg et al. 2004). However, as Williams and O'Reilly (1998) argued, this effect is not direct, nor is it unconditioned. Cognitive dynamics within diverse groups are complex, and as these authors argue, they can turn negative if differences are not adequately integrated and managed. The literature is inconclusive about the specific attributes that need to be explored to address the cognitive effects of diversity. Several papers have focused on the effects of tenure diversity (Choi 2007, Choi 2009; Chi et al. 2009) and functional background (Pelled et al. 1999; Choi 2007; Peters and Karren 2009), reporting no consistent results (Mello and Rentsch 2015). Educational diversity has also been addressed by empirical research with reference to differences in educational level and type of education of team members (Choi 2009; Curseu et al. 2012; Cummings et al. 2013). Broadly, while differences in the former have been associated with lower performance, heterogeneity in educational specialization has been considered beneficial for team performance (Curseu et al. 2012; Mello and Rentsch 2015).

Disciplinary diversity can be classified according to this second set of cognitive and task-oriented attributes. Various studies have specifically addressed how differences in the knowledge bases of scholars from different academic disciplines affect their collective performance. Cummings and Kiesler (2005), for instance, examined scientific collaboration within multidisciplinary teams and found that teams in which more disciplines are represented reported better research outcomes than less interdisciplinary teams. It was also confirmed that projects were more successful when more co-ordination mechanisms were used. Porac et al. (2004) studied scientific collaboration in two scientific teams. The first was formed by scientists from similar scholarly disciplines, while scientists on the second team had different backgrounds. The authors found that the multidisciplinary team had increased productivity, as measured by the number of publications. Stvilia et al. (2011) found that scientific teams with high disciplinary diversity showed more productivity, while team cohesion was positively related to team productivity. Similarly, in her study about individual researchers, Gonzalez-Brambila (2014) found that interdisciplinary research increases the publication productivity of researchers. Instead, Leahey et al. (2017) showed that multidisciplinary research involves fewer publications although higher citations; it was related to high risk and high reward efforts. Millar (2011) analysed the impacts of interdisciplinary research on early career of doctoral graduates.

However, as Perry-Smith and Vincent (2008) note, multidisciplinary teams also encounter problems. The authors establish that multidisciplinary teams benefit from professional composition and social networks, but conflict, identification, cohesion and co-operation problems arise at higher levels of multidisciplinaryity. In this line of research, Bercovitz and Feldman (2011) investigated creative teams of academic scientists and explored the co-ordination costs when teams are built with knowledge diversity among their members.

As Lee et al. (2015) note, large diverse-knowledge teams may benefit from broader knowledge domains but also exhibit declining marginal effects that impair team performance as heterogeneity increases. Cummings et al. (2013) found that although larger research groups were more productive than smaller ones, their productivity declined when members came from multiple disciplines or universities. Similarly, Dahlin et al. (2005) found that educational background diversity in small teams had non-linear effects on the range and depth of information use. The results suggest that teams with more educational diversity exhibit greater range and depth of information use, but only up to a point, at which returns start to diminish. This seems to be consistent with other papers on research collaboration, which suggest the existence of an optimal level of academic collaboration beyond which collaboration disrupts knowledge creation (Lavie and Drodi 2012).

Considering the above arguments, this paper suggests a non-linear relationship between the multidisciplinary of networks and research outputs (Figure 2). The cognitive diversity of researchers can improve the generation of knowledge and research output. On the other hand, diversity in knowledge bases can generate co-ordination costs and problems of understanding and communication when the optimal point of multidisciplinary is passed.

Consequently, we hypothesize the following:

Hypothesis 1: There is an inverted U-shaped curvilinear relationship between researchers' performance and the degree of multidisciplinary of their networks.

Figure 2. The relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance

Source: Own elaboration

A number of studies in the diversity field have also argued that to explain the extent to which the overall effects of diversity are positive or negative, it is necessary to introduce third variables for the specific conditions of the unit. Therefore, the consequences of diversity cannot be studied through direct models, as they may lead to contradictory findings. To respond to this, studies have proposed models of diversity–performance relationships and have included moderating variables, such as institutional, structural and context variables (Van Dijk et al. 2012). In view of the above discussion about the relational, cognitive and structural effects of

multidisciplinarity, we argue that this relationship may be moderated by researchers' social capital. Our review of the diversity literature leads us to believe that a certain stock of social capital could help researchers take advantage of the potential benefits of multidisciplinarity in scientific collaboration activities, as explained in the next section.

2.2. Social capital and research performance

The concept of social capital emerged in the field of sociology (Bourdieu 1986; Coleman 1988). Bourdieu (1986:21) defined it as 'the aggregate of the actual or potential resources which are linked to possession of a durable network of more or less institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition, or in other words, to membership in a group'. Coleman (1988:S98) refers social capital as 'a variety of different entities, with two elements in common: they all consist of some aspect of social structures, and they facilitate certain actions of actors - whether persons or corporate actors- within the structure'. The concept was quickly exported to other disciplines in the social sciences. This dissemination has led to the appearance of different conceptualizations in order to adapt the concept to the specific context analysed in each case. Consequently, numerous criticisms have arisen owing to the imprecision of the concept of social capital and the difficulties of applying it (Alguezaui and Filieri 2010; Rostila 2010).

In the management and organizational literature, the social capital concept has been primarily developed from the work of Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998:243). These authors established a theoretical framework with which to analyse social capital, which is defined as 'the sum of the actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or social unit'. The authors classified social capital into three highly interrelated dimensions (relational, cognitive and structural), which facilitate the creation and exchange of knowledge through social interactions, trust and the development of a shared vision among social network members (Nahapiet and Ghoshal 1998).

The *relational* dimension includes assets such as trust, norms, co-operation, commitment, obligations and identity (Nahapiet and Ghoshal 1998; Adler and Kwon 2002), which are acquired by people through social relations, encouraging them to share knowledge (Choi 2015). The literature has paid special attention to the trust dimension. Frequent and close interactions between actors generally strengthen the relationships, fostering trust (Tsai and Ghoshal 1998; McFadyen and Cannella 2004). A range of studies has shown that the higher the levels of trust, the more likely the actors are to co-operate and share their knowledge (Nahapiet and Ghosal 1998; Pardo et al. 2006; Todd et al. 2006). In this context, rules of co-operation and interaction are relevant for the creation and exchange of knowledge (Nahapiet and Ghoshal 1998). Without trust and behavioural norms, opportunistic behaviours may arise, making it difficult to share knowledge among actors (Gonzalez-Brambila 2014). In research groups, relational social capital embedded in the number of direct relationships and the strength of relationships, facilitates collaboration and knowledge sharing, which favours research performance (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013).

On the other hand, the *cognitive* dimension refers to the set of beliefs, values, language and codes shared by members of a social network, facilitating the understanding of common objectives (Chow and Chan 2008; Tsai and Ghoshal 1998). When social network members share a common language, contact among them is easier, enabling them to more easily obtain information. Shared visions and goals create values that facilitate the development of integrity

and shared responsibility (Leana and Pil 2006). In the research arena, the cumulative knowledge that researchers develop of their scientific field during their career is an asset that they bring to the group of collaborators. Researchers with greater tenure in the discipline accumulate more cognitive capital and can better apply and share knowledge of their discipline with others stimulating the achievement of research results (Li et al. 2013). In this sense, cognitive capital can be approximated by the researcher's experience in a discipline (Li et al. 2013), which encourages research collaboration and performance (Wang 2016)

Finally, the *structural* dimension refers to the patterns of social relations among members of the network, which are described mainly by network configurations (Nahapiet and Ghoshal 1998). The concept of the structural dimension is related to social networks (Zheng 2010). Social network theory provides two different perceptions of social capital that are relevant to the team diversity-performance literature: structural holes and closure network approaches (Reagans and Zuckerman 2001). The former approach to social capital is based on the existence of gaps between nodes in the social network (which is an open social structure); these gaps are recognized as structural holes, which can take advantage to connect clusters and obtain access to new and non-redundant information (Burt 1992). Structural holes enhance network information benefits (Burt 1992). Instead, the closure network approach refers to a closure perspective in which actors are connected to each other, acquiring a higher level of mutual trust and coordination and developing better communication skills (Coleman 1988). Dense networks facilitate the development of trust and shared norms and have the benefit of access to information. However, that information can become redundant promoting cooperation (Coleman 1988). As some papers argue, structural holes are more related to performance in contexts of knowledge exploration, while dense networks matter in knowledge exploitation contexts (Rowley et al. 2000). Some papers suggest that, due to forms of exchange and sharing knowledge among researchers, the information benefits of structural holes could be more relevant than those of closure networks in academic networks (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013), while other papers advocate for similar benefits for both measures of network structures (Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila 2016).

Thus defined, structural social capital describes the presence of a network of access to people and resources, while relational and cognitive social capital reflect the capacity for sharing resources within that network (Andrews 2010).

Studies applying social capital to the specific context of academic research are still limited, although they provide interesting arguments for the development of our theoretical framework. Gonzalez-Brambila (2014), for instance, analysed how different dimensions of social capital affected scientists' research productivity, measured by publications. The results of that study indicated that networks rich in structural holes were more relevant to productivity than sparse ones. At the same time, relational social capital and cognitive social capital measured as the number of ties of a specific researcher and the extent to which he/she publishes with researchers from different areas of knowledge respectively, also positively affected scientific productivity. Gonzalez-Brambila (2014) also concluded that the effects of social capital are highly dependent on the scholars' areas of knowledge. In a different study, Gonzalez-Brambila et al. (2013) explored the simultaneous effects of different dimensions of network embeddedness on both research output and impact. They found that relational ties between scientists account for quality but not for output, while collaboration across disciplinary boundaries is associated with increased output. Regarding the structural dimension, they concluded that the presence of

structural holes positively affected the number of citations. In a later empirical study, Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila (2016) found a positive relationship between the structural dimension of social capital (measured by structural holes and density) and publications and citations in the field of engineering. Abbasi et al. (2011) used social network analysis to examine the effect of social networks on the performance of researchers as measured by the number of citations. Their results indicated that the normalized degree of centrality, efficiency and average tie strength had a positive effect on research performance. Li et al. (2013) explained how the social capital embedded in the structure of a network was also related to a stronger impact of research. To model this relationship, they defined six indicators of social capital, analysing the interactions between them and their effects on the citations received. The results showed that betweenness centrality was the most influential structural factor on research impact, while other factors related to relational (prolific co-author count) and cognitive social capital (measured by the length of time someone had published in a discipline and by the degree of exploration in team composition) had an indirect effect on the number of citations.

As Gonzalez-Brambila et al. (2013) highlighted, access to new information is the principal direct benefit of social capital. Researchers belonging to multidisciplinary groups could benefit from direct and strong links with researchers from different knowledge backgrounds. This social interaction facilitates access to diverse knowledge, ideas and perspectives as well as the complementary assets and skills required for advanced research (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013; Perry-Smith and Vincent 2008; Gonzalez-Brambila 2014). At the same time, researchers could benefit from the resources available in the external academic community. Researchers from different backgrounds contribute to activities developed in multidisciplinary networks with relevant knowledge and expertise from their own disciplines, but they generally differ in their languages, experience and approaches to tasks. This cognitive heterogeneity may lead to task, process and integration conflicts, which could negatively affect group performance (Perry-Smith and Vincent 2008). Research suggests that factors such as direct and repeated interactions among group members may facilitate collaborative dynamics, promote higher levels of trust within groups, and help to manage conflicts (Perry-Smith and Vincent 2008). In view of this, we conclude that the greater the trust and identification of researchers with their collaborators, the greater their willingness to share knowledge and co-operate in the creation and diffusion of knowledge, which would help to dissolve potential conflicts. This moderating effect would make research networks perform better, helping them to maximize performance in conjunction with greater multidisciplinaryity.

Consequently, with respect to relational social capital, we hypothesize the following:

Hypothesis 2: High direct ties positively moderate the relationship between multidisciplinaryity and researchers' performance.

Hypothesis 3: Strong relationships in the network positively moderate the relationship between multidisciplinaryity and researchers' performance.

Regarding cognitive social capital, we hypothesize the following:

Hypothesis 4: High experience of researchers in their disciplines positively moderates the relationship between multidisciplinaryity and researchers' performance.

Regarding structural social capital, we hypothesize the following:

Hypothesis 5: Dense relationships in the network positively moderate the relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance.

Hypothesis 6: Rich relationships in structural holes positively moderate the relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance.

Figure 3 depicts how the curvilinear effect of multidisciplinary on research performance would change as levels of social capital increase ($CS_1 < CS_2 < CS_3$). The moderating effect would make the curve taller and wider, allowing networks to perform better and placing the optimum value at higher levels of disciplinary diversity.

Figure 3. Effects of social capital

Source: Own graphic

3. Methodology and data

3.1. Sample and data collection

Data on researchers were collected and derived from the international population of researchers in the field of management attending the 2017 European Academy of Management (EURAM) conference. EURAM is one of the most important annual conferences dedicated to the advancement of the academic discipline of management in Europe. The international character of this congress, the high degree of diversity, the wide variety of tracks it covers, the specialization in the field of management and its relevance in the advancement of the discipline provide an accuracy criterion for the data collection. A self-response questionnaire was delivered to researchers to measure issues related to their intellectual (capital human, social and organizational dimensions), and some demographic and professional aspects of research (e.g., university, country, gender, years of research experience). To calculate social network

measures, in addition to the questionnaire information, we extracted information about respondents' networks of collaborations, as well as their results. To do so, we used the Scopus database. We decided to use the Scopus considering that it provided a better coverage in the field of management, comprising a wider range of outputs than Web of Science (Mingers and Lipitakis 2010)¹. In addition, it offered easy extraction of the number of publications as well as the h-index metrics of each scholar, and co-authors. Co-authorship is used to establish the network of collaborators of each researcher. Two researchers are considered connected if they are co-authors of at least one publication jointly in the analysed period, so publications with a single author are not considered. In our sample, we consider all publications, including books, book chapters, and procedures that are part of the researchers' performance and that result from the collaboration during the period 2000-2016.

We also use this database to identify the disciplinary profile of both the researchers in the sample and their respective co-authors. Scopus provides 27 different subject areas in which classify the journals. The field of research is considered as the two subject areas in which the author has published the most publications according to the Scopus database. Forty-five scholars in the initial sample had to be removed because they had single-author papers, they could not be identified in Scopus, or they did not have publication registers. Therefore, the dataset was composed of 110 academic respondents.

3.2. Variables

Researcher performance (dependent variable)

Measuring the scientific performance of researchers is an increasingly important task for the academic community because almost all research evaluation decisions depend on the merits of research (Alonso et al. 2009). The literature provides different metrics by which to measure scholars' research performance. In this paper, we opted to use the *h-index*², proposed by Hirsch (2005). Drawing on his definition, 'a scientist has an h-index if h of his or her N_p papers have at least h citations each, and the other $(N_p - h)$ papers have $\leq h$ citations each' (Hirsch 2005:16569). The h-index is based on the largest number of articles included that have had at least the same number of citations. This indicator has received criticism because it does not take into account the length of the scientific career, the effect of co-authorship or the journal quality (Kelly and Jennions 2006; Batista et al. 2006; Hirsch 2010). It is important to note that these inconveniences are shared with almost any indicator that is based on dating counts (Alonso et al. 2009). Despite this, the h-index is one of the best-known scientific performance measures, and it is widely used by the academic community to evaluate research results (Abbasi et al. 2011; Cimenler et al. 2014). Its value lies in providing an external and objective measure, which combines in a single indicator both the quantity and impact of publications. It is a dynamic index and change when the researchers include publications or cites. Not all papers contribute in a similar way to the h-index, that is, publications with a low number of citations will never

¹ Scopus covers a broad range of source types such as peer-reviewed journals, open access journals, conference proceedings, trade publications and book series. It covers 22,800 titles from more than 5,000 international publishers with 8,698 active titles in Social Sciences. The Scopus database also covers different document types such as articles, in press articles, books, chapters, conference papers, editorials, erratum, letters, notes, reviews, and short surveys. It does not cover neither conference meeting abstracts nor book reviews (<https://www.elsevier.com>).

² H-index includes self-citations, which although can increase its score, the effect seems to be small (Hirsch 2005).

contribute to the h-index of researchers (Hirsh 2005). It means that not everything counts, only quality publications. Additionally, it is easy to obtain the necessary data, and the index is not sensitive to low and high values, among other advantages (Batista et al. 2006; Huang 2012). To ensure academic rigour, we used the h-index calculated by Scopus, which includes all publications incorporated in this database.

Multidisciplinarity

The groups composed of multidisciplinary members have different disciplinary backgrounds, generating more creative solutions and more innovative results as well as better research results (Cummings et al. 2013). While there are different measures to assess the degree of multidisciplinarity in researchers' networks, we opted to use Blau's (1977) index, which is a diversity measure usually adopted by the workforce diversity literature (Richard et al. 2004; Pitts 2005). The Blau's index is defined as $[1 - \sum p_i^2]$, where p is the proportion of researchers in the respective discipline and i is the number of disciplines represented in the academic research network. The Blau's index values vary between zero and $(k-1)/k$; the higher the Blau's index, the greater the disciplinary diversity among group members (Solanas et al. 2016).

As explained above, to identify researchers' disciplinary profile, we turn to the subject areas of Scopus database in which they have their publications. Given that researchers could have publications in more than one area of knowledge, we considered the multidisciplinarity of the authors from the two subject areas in which the author has published the most publications according to the categories of the Scopus database (level 1).

Social capital

In the university context, social capital is usually examined through the analysis of co-authorship networks (Li et al. 2013; Gonzalez-Brambila 2014). Empirical papers focused on the relationship between researchers' social capital and research results have mainly used social network analysis techniques to evaluate this relation (Gonzalez-Brambila 2014; Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013; Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila 2016; Abbasi et al. 2011; Li et al. 2013).

In our study, we have 110 researchers and 925 co-authors. As we focused on the local networks of the researchers, we built one-mode matrices that relate the researchers to their co-authors (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013). As the papers focus on the local social networks of researchers, we built a different matrix for each researcher. Specifically, we create a 110 relational matrix based on the adjacency matrix. It takes the value 1 if researchers i and j co-authored at least one paper and 0 otherwise; the diagonals of the matrix are ignored because co-authoring with oneself has no meaning in this context. From the adjacency matrix, a new matrix was calculated to measure the strength of the ties through the number of co-authored papers (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013). The value network considers how many times the authors had written a paper with each of their co-authors.

This paper applies Social Network Analysis to measure social capital using the software UCINET (Borgatti et al. 2002). The relational, cognitive and structural dimensions of social capital are determined through the analysis of the structure and configuration of the collaborative research networks of each researcher. Specifically, we employ the variables *direct*

ties and the *strength of ties* to measure relational social capital, *first paper* variable as a measure of cognitive social capital, and the variables *density* and *structural holes* to measure structural social capital.

Direct ties. The number of *direct ties* is the number of co-authors that a researcher has at a given time. In our case, this is the total number of co-authors of the researcher in the period considered (2000-2016). It is expected that researchers with more direct ties tend to combine and exchange resources more easily among the members of their networks, allowing researchers to access new knowledge and experiences (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013).

Strength of ties. The *strength of ties* approximates the frequency with which a researcher publishes with his or her co-authors. We measured the strength of ties of each researcher by counting the number of times the researcher published with each author during the 2000-2016 period. Co-publication provides the opportunity to develop jointly held resources (McFayden and Cannella 2004).

First paper. The *first paper* variable was included to measure cognitive social capital. Li et al. (2013) pointed out that period of time during which someone has published in a discipline is a way to accumulate and develop cognitive capital. Similarly, we calculated the *first paper* variable as the time elapsed (in years) since the researcher published his/her first paper. Data come from Scopus.

Density. *Density* is a concept widely used in network theory to measure the network structure and is used to describe the global level of relationships between nodes in a network. In a scientific collaboration network, the density is the proportion of existing relationships in relation to the possible relationships (Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila 2016). The total of possible relationships is calculated by multiplying the total number of nodes by the total number of nodes minus one. The density of a network is considered high if many actors or nodes are connected to each other.

Structural holes. *Structural holes* are the separation of different actors who are not connected to each other. This variable was obtained by subtracting 1-Constraint (Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila 2016). The Constraint (c_i) is an index that measures the degree to which a researcher's contacts are redundant and it is obtained through Burt's formula (Buskens and Van de Rijt 2008).

$$C_i = \sum_{j \neq i} (p_{ij} + \sum_{k \neq i, k \neq j} p_{ik} p_{kj})^2$$

where p_{ij} is the proportion of time that researcher i has spent in contact with researcher j .

Control variable. To reduce potential omitted variable bias, we introduce other variables that previous studies have shown to affect researchers' performance. Several papers have provided evidence of the Matthew effect (Merton 1968) at individual, institutional and country levels of the science system (Lavirière and Gringas 2010). To control for this cumulative advantage in science we focused on reputation of researchers. Researchers' reputation at the individual level

is generally measured through publications and especially through citations (Stephan 1996). As our dependent variable (h-index) considers both publications and citations, we include the *Reputation* variable associated with the reputation of the researcher's host institution to capture the potential Matthew effect. There is a potential interaction between Matthew effects at individual and institutional levels (Rigney 2010). Similarly to other studies, this variable is measured by the year of the foundation of the university (e.g., Audretsch and Lehmann 2005); it is retrieved from universities' web pages.

Prior studies have also found that personal attributes of researchers, such as gender, influence their performance (Ledin et al. 2007; Barrios et al. 2013; Badar et al. 2015) but with contradictory results. We operationalize the *gender* variable through a dummy variable coded 1 for males and 0 for females.

4. Results and discussion

Due to the nature of the dependent variable, regression Poisson models have been estimated with the objective of testing the hypotheses established in section 2. Table 1 reports the means and standard deviations as well as minimum and maximum values, and Table 2 reports the correlations of the variables introduced in further analyses.

As shown in Table 3, seven models were estimated. Model I tests the effect of multidisciplinary on researchers' performance, as described in hypothesis 1. As can be observed, the linear term of the *multidisciplinary* variable is positively and significantly related to the h-index. The results show that the variety of knowledge, experience, ideas, and perspectives within multidisciplinary groups can increase the performance of researchers by generating more creative and innovative ideas (Huang and Li 2010). The result does not change when the quadratic term of the variable is introduced. The estimated β for the quadratic term (*multidisciplinary*²) is negative and significant, confirming that the effects of this variable on scholars' h-indexes can be depicted as an inverted U-shaped relationship. The curvilinear relationship between multidisciplinary and performance shows that the diversity of disciplines within a group has positive effects on the performance of researchers to an optimal point, in which these effects diminish. Researchers have been trained in different fields with different ways of working, so some problems may arise related to a lack of cohesion, difficulty in coordination, tasks and relationship conflicts that may affect negatively to the performance (Van Knippenberg et al. 2004).

To test the rest of the hypothesis, the five variables describing social capital dimensions were introduced as moderators of the relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance (Models II to VII). Models II, III and IV show the results when each of the social capital dimensions—relational, cognitive and structural—was introduced separately in the econometric estimations. It is known that the three dimensions are interdependent, but they are introduced individually for analytical purposes (Nahapiet and Ghoshal 1998). In Model II, the coefficients of the interaction terms for measuring the moderating effect of *Direct ties* and the *strength of ties* relational social capital were positive and significant. These results support hypotheses 2 and 3, respectively. In multidisciplinary groups researchers who have more direct and strong ties with collaborators tend to have higher h-indexes. This may be due, on the one

hand, to the fact that a researcher with a greater number of direct ties has greater access to the combination and exchange of resources, ideas and information (González-Brambila et al. 2013), and on the other hand, strong ties build trust among members, reducing the problems of cohesion and coordination of multidisciplinary groups. Therefore, not only the number of direct ties that the researchers maintain but also the quality of those ties condition the effect of multidisciplinary on the researchers' performance.

Similarly, the estimated β of the interaction term of *First paper* was significant and positively related to the h-index (Model III). This result supports hypothesis 4. Researchers from different disciplines use different methodologies, publish in different journals and attend different conferences accumulating experience in their disciplines. Therefore, in multidisciplinary groups researchers with more cumulative experience in their scientific domain possess and benefit from higher cognitive capital that, in turn, leads to higher performance.

Two measures have been introduced in Model IV to analyse the moderating effect of structural social capital. The coefficient of the interaction term of *Structural holes* is positive and significant, while it is not significant for the interaction term of *Density*. Previous studies have shown that networks rich in structural holes have a predominant role in the academic context and that dense networks support the generation of knowledge (Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2013). These results reject hypothesis 5 and confirm hypothesis 6. This suggests that a well-positioned researcher on the network will have access to non-redundant information and a variety of ideas, favourably influencing performance.

Model VII includes the effect of multidisciplinary and all social capital variables on researchers' performance. Due to the high correlation between the two structural social capital variables *Density* and *Structural holes*, two different models have also been estimated, including each variable separately (models V and VI, respectively). When all social capital variables are introduced together, they are still significant, except for the density of the network, showing their moderating effect on the relationship between multidisciplinary and the h-index. Therefore, we find evidence that the relational, cognitive and structural social capitals of network members positively moderate the curvilinear relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance: the curve is taller and the optimum is reached with higher levels of disciplinary diversity. These results confirm our hypothesis that to mitigate the conflict and communication problems that appear as multidisciplinary increases, research networks should foster frequent and smooth interactions among members, building a collaborative climate that facilitates the exchange of ideas and knowledge-sharing in which both the expertise and publishing tenure of researchers are relevant factors.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
1	H-Index	4.1727	5.1059	0	23
2	Multidisciplinarity	0.5125	0.3624	0	0.95
3	Direct ties	13.2273	18.7302	0	144
4	Strength of ties	1.0121	0.6618	0	3
5	First paper	8.2545	5.6721	0	28
6	Density	0.3302	0.3220	0	1
7	Structural holes	0.6124	0.3252	0	1
8	Reputation	1852.855	220.9379	1088	2005
9	Gender	0.5455	0.5002	0	1

Table 2. Correlations

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 H-Index	1								
2 Multidisciplinarity	0.0535	1							
3 Direct ties	0.7580	0.0871	1						
4 Strength of ties	0.2294	0.1592	-0.0449	1					
5 First paper	0.5758	0.0613	0.4313	0.2519	1				
6 Density	-0.2642	0.0293	-0.1813	-0.1015	-0.3532	1			
7 Structural holes	0.4724	-0.0748	0.4703	-0.1195	0.4550	-0.6693	1		
8 Reputation	0.0259	-0.0728	0.0786	-0.0704	0.0405	0.0068	0.0120	1	
9 Gender	0.1203	0.0446	0.1316	-0.0012	0.0811	0.1023	0.0847	-0.0384	1

Table 3. Results of the regression analysis

	Model I	Model II	Model III	Model IV	Model V	Model VI	Model VII
Constant	-0.1850 (0.7690)	0.6700 (0.6566)	0.8330 (0.7239)	0.6280 (0.6854)	1.3171 (0.6298)	1.2480 (0.5705)	1.2257 (0.5731)
Multidisciplinary	6.9933*** (2.2777)	5.3196*** (2.0419)	4.5181* (2.4044)	1.3494 (2.1363)	3.8184* (2.0342)	1.4753 (2.2347)	1.2069 (2.1786)
Multidisciplinary ²	-7.6934*** (2.2928)	-6.7381*** (1.932)	-5.7706** (2.2572)	-4.7950*** (1.9484)	-5.4813*** (1.9349)	-4.8858*** (1.8212)	-4.9269*** (1.8461)
Multidisciplinary × Direct ties		0.2348*** (0.0042)			0.0287*** (0.0041)	0.0122*** (0.0041)	0.0109*** (0.0041)
Multidisciplinary × Strength of ties		0.7165*** (0.2117)			0.4181* (0.2187)	0.4403** (0.1896)	0.4659** (0.2019)
Multidisciplinary × First paper			0.1184*** (0.0363)		0.0915*** (0.0309)	0.0798*** (0.0287)	0.0807*** (0.0284)
Multidisciplinary × Density				0.6788 (0.4636)	-1.0167 (0.6180)		0.3877 (0.4884)
Multidisciplinary × Structural holes				4.5535*** (0.7395)		2.4804*** (0.8356)	2.7474*** (0.8548)
Reputation	0.0003 (0.0004)	-0.0000 (0.0003)	-0.0001 (0.0004)	-0.0000 (0.0003)	-0.0003 (0.0004)	-0.0003 (0.0003)	-0.0003 (0.0003)
Gender	0.2380 (0.2251)	0.1058 (0.2121)	0.1439 (0.2246)	0.1040 (0.2052)	0.0821 (0.2069)	0.0702 (0.1946)	0.0657 (0.1948)
	Wald χ^2 χ^2 (4) = 17.12	χ^2 (6) = 58.76	χ^2 (5) = 37.37	χ^2 (6) = 85.15	χ^2 (8) = 130.00	χ^2 (8) = 133.86	χ^2 (9) = 133.55
	Log pseudolikelihood -368.99638	-308.79818	-320.50332	-299.33834	-280.54928	-269.37455	-269.11278
	Pseudo R² 0.1049	0.2510	0.2226	0.2739	0.3195	0.3466	0.3472

N = 110. robust standard errors are in parentheses. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

5. Conclusions

In the last few decades, science has undergone significant changes in which scientific collaboration and research conducted by multidisciplinary teams becoming relevant (Cummings and Kiesler 2014). Multidisciplinary collaboration have been encouraged and supported by policy makers, requiring cross-disciplinary boundaries and, often, also organizational ones (Cummings and Kiesler 2005).

The paper was designed to raise a better understanding of the relationship between multidisciplinary and the researchers' performance and to explain how the assess embedded in social relationships of research groups results in greater performance of researchers. Although different empirical studies have recently been conducted to evaluate the general impact of multidisciplinary, there is a lack of evidence about the internal processes that it triggers. The literature has also highlighted the need to study the conditions under which the overall effect of multidisciplinary turns positive or negative, as previous studies have found contradictory findings in this sense. The present study sought to fill this gap by investigating the possible moderating effect of researchers' social capital. In this sense, the paper contributes to the extant literature on team diversity explaining that multidisciplinary has two different but related effects on performance. At lower and moderate levels of multidisciplinary, research networks benefit from the diversity of perspectives and cognitive approaches that scholars from different backgrounds bring to the network. This effect disappears at higher levels of multidisciplinary when differences are so evident that the diversity of perspectives cannot be reconciled. In these cases, task conflict and communicational difficulties are more likely to appear, dissolving the positive cognitive consequences. This paper proposes that this relationship can be described as an inverted U-shaped relationship (Figure 2), which was confirmed by the estimation of regression models.

The results also confirmed that the curvilinear effect of multidisciplinary on research performance is not unconditional. The paper contributes to social capital literature investigating the possible moderating effect of researchers' social capital in that relationship. According to the proposed theoretical model, we conclude that social capital moderates this relationship. The estimation of the seven regression models showed that fostering relational, cognitive and structural social capital among the members of the network could mitigate the negative consequences of multidisciplinary, which may appear when this variable reaches its optimum value.

As the empirical analysis also confirmed, all the dimensions of social capital help to manage internal dynamics within multidisciplinary research networks. Positive internal dynamics within multidisciplinary research networks require deeper connections among collaborators, that is numerous and strong direct ties, and these connections are linked to trust and knowledge sharing. At the same time, the length of researchers' careers and their cumulative knowledge of their own scientific fields seem to facilitate the research processes internal to the group, thus alleviating the negative effects of multidisciplinary. Particularly interesting is the result obtained for the structural dimension of social capital, for which the interaction term of the density variable is not significant, but it is significant for structural holes, confirming that networks rich in structural holes are more relevant to the results of research than are dense networks with redundant information.

The results of this paper offer interesting implications for both academics and research institutions. First, the paper provides new evidence of the importance of multidisciplinary research to achieve greater performance of researchers, suggesting that there is an optimal level of disciplinary diversity for research groups from which, performance can be negatively affected. Second, the paper highlights the crucial role of social capital facilitating a greater degree of multidisciplinary of research groups. The analysis shows how institutions and research leaders could take advantage of disciplinary diversity of research groups and mitigate its potential difficulties, through the built of relational, cognitive and structural social capital.

Nevertheless, this research is not exempt from limitations that condition the scope and generalization of its results. On the one hand, it would be interesting to see whether the results of our analysis are maintained when other metrics are used to measure the performance of the researchers. On the other hand, we must take into account that the analyses have been developed from a sample of scholars from a single discipline (management). Although this sample helps to provide consistency for the results obtained, it obviously conditions the extent to which conclusions can be generalized. Further research would be necessary to confirm whether internal dynamics and co-ordination mechanisms differ in other academic fields in which research processes are substantially different. The research design proposed in this paper, based on Social Network Analysis to measure social capital, has provided interesting insight into the internal dynamics of research networks, but a deeper empirical analysis would be necessary to fully understand the structure of relationships between academics from different disciplines beyond social science. Social network analysis provides interesting tools for this purpose, i.e., to describe and represent the social structures of different research fields. By studying the internal dynamics of different fields, research could explain the mechanisms through which academic social capital fosters scientific advancement through the connection of different disciplines and the establishment of knowledge-sharing bridges. The conclusions of our study invite future research that could extend and contrast the findings obtained here.

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